

A Data Quality Glossary

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Data quality is commonly defined as *fitness for use*, i.e., the fitness of data for a particular purpose or application. This general definition is usually broken down into a set of **data quality dimensions** or criteria, which are partly subjective, partly objective. Some of them can be measured automatically, some are verifiable, and some can be assessed only by experts.

This data quality glossary lists all relevant data quality dimensions with a concise but general definition. The focus lies on the use of data for artificial intelligence applications. The dimensions are not to be seen as orthogonal – their assessments may depend on one another; still, each dimension views data quality from a slightly different perspective. Where dimensions or terms with identical wording have already been taken up in laws, the glossary contains a corresponding reference.* Some classic dimensions stemming from the literature on data quality (e.g., objectivity, compliance) are differentiated here in more detail or broken down into several elements. In future editions of the glossary, we plan to systematically add examples as well as link appropriate literature. We welcome comments and questions about the terms and their definitions: felix.naumann@hpi.de.

**It should be noted that this glossary considers the European legal framework and that within other jurisdictions the dimensions may have been regulated differently. Where no harmonised European law with direct effect exists, the national law of Germany is analysed. Furthermore, the EU Commission's AI Act draft cited here is still an ongoing legislative process. Accordingly, it cannot be said with certainty in what form the law will actually enter into force. In any case, the final version will contain changes compared to the draft.*

Accessibility

Accessibility has technical, organisational, financial, and legal components. Technical accessibility ensures sufficient resources (computer, network) at each point of processing to allow smooth and fast access. Organisational accessibility allows users without technological tools or technical knowledge to easily access the data. Legal accessibility results from licensing of legally protected datasets, which allows for continued use of the data, while financial accessibility can be achieved through reasonable or waived user fees.

Related terms: Response time, latency, openness, availability, discoverability, transparency

Accuracy

Accuracy describes the correspondence between a phenomenon in the world and its description as data. When comparing the data value with the empirically ascertainable value, the difference can be determined either in binary terms (equal or unequal) or the degree of difference can be determined by means of a similarity measure (e.g., as the similarity on a scale from 0 to 1). Accuracy plays a role especially for data whose factual correctness can be conclusively determined and whose meaning is not ambivalent.

Related terms: Correctness, free of error

Legal background:

Article 10 (3) sentence 1 of the AI Act refers to the accuracy of data. It speaks of "error-free" data; in the original English wording, the Commission uses the term "free of errors". The European Commission bases the legal terms of the AI Act on common IT definitions.

In reference to personal data, the guarantee of accuracy is prescribed by the GDPR in Art. 5(1)(d). The English version uses the term "accurate", the German version "factual correctness" (*sachliche Richtigkeit*).

Added value

The added value of data refers to the efficient utilisation of data in an application. Data are efficiently utilised if their use results in a profit (monetary, knowledge) for the data owners or the application's users.

Appropriate amount of data

The amount of data describes the size of the dataset and can be measured, for example, as the number of bytes or the number of rows. It can be too small or too large; for example, a certain amount of training data is needed to adequately train an AI model. Conversely, an excessive amount of data, such as unnecessarily high-resolution image files, can lead to data management issues.

Related terms: Conciseness

Balance

The balance of data considers the distribution of data points within a dataset. A dataset is balanced if the data points within the represented range of values are equally distributed in relation to each other. For example, in a balanced dataset that divides clients into age groups, clients of all ages should be equally represented. This does not mean that all age groups of the total population must be included (see *diversity*).

Related terms: Diversity, representativity

Completeness

Completeness is the relationship between the amount of data represented and the amount of data to be represented. While the former can be counted (number of rows, number of non-null values), the latter can often only be estimated.

A dataset (e.g., table) is complete with respect to a domain if every entity in the domain is represented in the dataset. A dataset (e.g., row) is complete if there is a value for each attribute (column).

Related terms: Missing values

Legal background:

Art. 10 para. 3 p. 1 AI Act proposes that training, testing and validation data must be complete. The European Commission bases the legal terms of the AI Act on common IT definitions.

Concise representation

Concise representation considers in what form data are represented. Concise data are presented in a suitable and clearly recognisable way, depending on their intended use.

An example of this are stock prices, which are displayed in a line chart so that price developments over a certain period of time can be observed easily. However, the inclusion of too many stock price trends or the consideration of too large retrospectives can limit the readability – the data is not represented concisely.

Related terms: Clear presentation, compactness

Consistency

A dataset (e.g., a table) is consistent if all conditions imposed on the state of the dataset are met. Consistency includes integrity conditions such as data types or value ranges, dependencies or even relationships across different datasets. Examples of a lack of consistency include different date formats in a column, different cities for the same zip code, or purchase orders with invalid customer numbers.

Related terms: Integrity, constraints, validity

Consistent representation

A dataset (e.g., a table) is consistent in its representation if no attribute (column) has two or more unique values that are semantically equivalent (e.g., New York vs. NYC or 1/12/2022 vs. 12/1/2022). This includes exact duplicates.

Related terms: Uniform representation, categorical duplicates

Cost

The cost of a dataset includes both the monetary costs incurred in generating or acquiring and permanently storing the data, and the personnel costs incurred in acquiring and preparing the data. Costs may be calculated for an entire dataset or per query to the data.

Examples: Annotation of data by data stewards, or crowd-workers; purchase of data from data brokers; storage in the cloud; personnel costs, e.g., for cleaning, reformatting, etc.

Related terms: Price

Credibility

Data credibility is shaped by multiple characteristics, including psychological markers (unconscious assumptions, stereotypes), social markers (recognised titles and institutions, source authority), aesthetic markers (familiar display conventions in the design of charts or a web page), and cognitive markers (readability, expertise of the viewer). Credibility is usually a contextual and partly subjective quality of data, information, and their origin. Accordingly, it cannot be represented exclusively as a statistical quantity.

Related terms: Believability, trustworthiness, reputation, authority

Diversity

A dataset is diverse if each type of entity of the total set occurs at least once. The goal is that the dataset reflects the diversity of entity types from the total set, i.e., contains all relevant variants. For instance, if an employee database (total set) consists of male and female employees and the department they work in has been recorded in addition to gender: The dataset is diverse if it contains at least one female employee and one male employee from each department.

Related terms: Representativity, balance

Documentation

A dataset is well documented if relevant, complete and correct structured metadata as well as a textual description are available. Typical metadata include the volume of the data, its technical (data types) and semantic (table and column names) schema, statistics, as well as information about its provenance and any transformation that has been performed so far. Textual descriptions, which can be formalised in so-called data sheets, include the data's purpose and their previous use(s).

Related terms: Metadata, description, transparency

Ease of manipulation

Data are manipulable if changes or additions can be made easily (data in an Excel spreadsheet vs. data on a website). Manipulability can be viewed from both a positive and a negative perspective: on the one hand, there is a risk that data will – intentionally or unintentionally – be falsified (negative case). On the other hand, manipulable data can be easily adapted for legitimate individual purposes (positive case).

Related terms: Manipulability, editability, interoperability

Efficiency

Data efficiency describes how resource-efficiently various processes or algorithms (e.g., sorting algorithms or data analysis methods) can be applied to the data. Resources can include programming effort, computing power, or energy consumption. Accordingly, data are efficient if they are easy to use and effectively support a variety of processes.

Related terms: Sustainability, cost effectiveness

Fairness

Fairness in the context of AI systems is concerned with identifying, analysing, and quantifying biases that discriminate against individuals and groups on the basis of certain characteristics, such as gender, ethnicity, or disability. Consequently, an AI system is fair if it meets standards for freedom from discriminatory bias according to certain metrics. Data in an AI context cannot be inherently fair, but the structure and quality of datasets can have a strong impact on biases and the potential fairness of AI systems. Data-specific biases can occur due to a lack of balance or diversity in the representation of social groups and their perspectives, for example as a result of inappropriate selection methods.

Related terms: Justice, bias

Legal Background:

According to the English language version of the GDPR, personal data must in principle be processed "fairly". However, the German language version, among others, which translates fairness with the German legal term *Treu und Glauben* ("good faith"), shows that the principle is not aimed at fairness in the sense of freedom from discrimination. It merely serves as a catch-all for cases that are not covered by the other protective provisions of the GDPR but could nevertheless significantly upset the balance it seeks to strike between the interests of the data subject and the data controller. [Art. 5(1)(a) Alt. 2 DS-GVO] (Roßnagel/NK-Datenschutzrecht, 1st edition 2019, Art. 5 para. 47).

The fact that the term fairness is not necessarily understood in the same way in a German-speaking legal context is also shown by the General Equal Treatment Act (*Allgemeines Gleichbehandlungsgesetz*, AGG for short). This law also deals with protection against discrimination (for certain characteristics, cf. Section 1 AGG), but does not use the term fairness. Instead, the prevention or elimination of disadvantages (*Benachteiligungen*) is

mentioned. The English versions of the European directives on discrimination (e.g. COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2000/43/EC) also use the term discrimination instead of fairness. It is important to note that there are permissible and impermissible forms of discrimination. Discrimination in the sense of §3 para.1, 2 AGG occurs if a person receives less favourable treatment than another individual in a comparable situation because of a certain characteristic (cf. §1 AGG) (direct discrimination), or if an apparently neutral provision, criterion or practice disadvantages persons because of certain characteristics (indirect discrimination). These disadvantages become impermissible only if they are not justified; for example, discrimination can be justified if it pursues an objective goal and the chosen means to achieve this goal are necessary and appropriate.

Portability

Portability describes the ability to transfer structured data reliably and securely from one system to another. A simple transferral of personal data from a social network to an external data storage device would be an example of good portability. Portable data is formatted according to common standards.

Related terms: Transferability

Precision

Precision, on the one hand, measures the degree of variance of repeatedly recorded data under unchanged conditions. This must be strictly distinguished from data *accuracy* (see there). An example of high precision is when one of a hospital patient's vital sign parameters is measured precisely every 120 seconds. However, the data's accuracy – for example regarding measurement errors – cannot be inferred from this precisely timed recording. On the other hand, precision is used as a measure of the level of detail of information. For example, a form may ask for the year of birth or the exact date of birth. One indicator of precision is the number of decimal digits in measured values. A third aspect of precision is the exactness of predefined value classes, e.g., when distinguishing between “brown” and “black” while specifying skin colour.

Related terms: Exactness

Privacy

Data are private if the persons described in the data have control over and access to that data. Private (also confidential) data protects the user's right to informational self-determination. The legal protection of privacy can be ensured organisationally and technically: organisational privacy can be established through consent declarations by users, which can prohibit the entire use of the data or contain instructions for use (partial deletion, processing, etc.). For the technical establishment of privacy, the data can for example be encrypted or physical access to the storage medium can be restricted.

Related terms: Confidentiality, data protection

Legal Background:

Privacy as such is not a specific legal requirement, but as an expression of the fundamental right to informational self-determination or protection of privacy, it is the protection target of data protection law. Particularly the GDPR contributes to the protection of privacy in the context of personal data with a catalogue of rights and obligations.

Recoverability

Data are recoverable if they are stored redundantly and securely, e.g. on a separate storage medium. This ensures the recoverability of lost data, for example in the event of system errors or the loss of data carriers. In addition to recoverability itself, this dimension can be measured based on the time it takes to fully recover data.

Related terms: Error recovery, resilience

Relevance

Data is relevant if – from the user's point of view or for the purpose of an application – it contains necessary information and thus contributes to the concrete realisation of an objective. For example, in an online store, the name and price of an article are relevant for the comparability of products. The number of people involved in manufacturing the individual products, on the other hand, can be of little relevance, depending on the use case.

In the context of data protection, data can consist only of necessary entries and be collected and processed as is necessary for the purpose in question. In this context, it is essential that data are in a state or in a volume that complies with the applicable legal provisions. Thus, with the aim of data economy, the address of a customer may not be a mandatory entry when registering for a newsletter.

Related terms: Adequacy, significance

Legal Background:

Art. 10 (3) p. 1 AI Act requires that training data used for high-risk systems are confronted with relevant training, testing and validation data. In this context, the European Commission bases the legal terms of the AI Act on common IT definitions.

The data protection principle of "data minimisation" requires, according to Article 5 (1) (c) of the GDPR that personal data must be "adequate" and "relevant" in relation to the purpose.

Reliability

Reliability refers to an ideal state in which data have been collected without being influenced by bias. Collected data are reliable if they are identical regardless of who collected them.

Related terms: Objectivity

Representativity

A dataset is statistically representative if each entity of the total set to be represented has the same chance of being represented in it. Thus, the relative distributions of the characteristic

properties of the total set are reflected in the dataset. Closely related to statistical representativity – but still to be considered separately – are the dimensions of *balance* (see there) and *diversity* (see there).

For example: A dataset (total set) consists of 70 male and 30 female students. Of the male students, 40 study art and 30 history, while 15 of the female students study art and the remaining 15 history. Based on the previously stated total, a dataset would be representative if it consisted of 9 each of female art and history students, as well as 24 male art students and 18 male history students. This dataset is statistically representative because the relative ratios between students of the same sex, as well as the ratios between students of the same major are identical when compared to the total set.

Related terms: Coverage, diversity, balance

Legal Background:

Article 10 (3) p. 1 of the European Commission's draft AI Regulation mentions representativity as a requirement for datasets in high-risk systems. A legal definition is not given. However, Art. 10(3)(2) provides that the datasets used "shall have the appropriate statistical properties, including, where applicable, as regards the persons or groups of persons on which the high-risk AI system is intended to be used." Also, the datasets "shall take into account, to the extent required by the intended purpose, the characteristics or elements that are particular to the specific geographical, behavioural or functional setting within which the high-risk AI system is intended to be used. Art. 10(4) AI Act.

It is unclear whether a dataset is representative in the sense of the AI Act if it simply reflects the ratios of the total quantity to be represented in real terms, as shown in the example above. This is because the amount of data for marginal groups might not be sufficient to train the AI system to be used on those groups (see *appropriate amount of data*). However, the purpose of representativity is precisely to ensure that the trained AI system works for all populations to which it is meant to be applied. Also considering the concretisations by Art. 10 para. 3 sentence 2, para. 4 AI Act, it might therefore be beneficial to require a criterion of "probability of success", at least for human-related application areas. This criterion would be fulfilled in datasets that correctly reflect the circumstances of the corresponding groups of people. At the minimum, datasets should contain sufficient data for an individual group so that a trained system can with sufficient probability be used on this group.

Reputation

The reputation of data describes the trustworthiness of the data source and the processing system. Data and data sources enjoy a high reputation if they have already proven to be of high quality in the past and over a period of time. If no or only poor experience has been gained with them in the past, their reputation is low. In particular, if other data quality dimensions, such as *accuracy*, cannot be adequately measured, reputation is a relevant dimension that can also be understood as the *expected* quality of data.

Related terms: Trustworthiness, believability, credibility, authority

Security

The security of data describes the protection that exists at all times against unauthorised access to the data and against their theft or damage. Systems must guarantee correct access management; to maintain this guarantee, the functional security of a system is therefore also relevant, so that in the event of a functional failure the system will still enter a defined state in which the security of the data is guaranteed. For example, a customer of an online store should have access only to the orders they have previously placed and not to the sales figures of all products. Data should always be protected from hacker attacks, in which attackers could steal or encrypt the data.

Related terms: Privacy, integrity

Timeliness

The real world is subject to continuous changes: Stock prices fluctuate, products are sold, football matches are played, and people readjust their habits to their environment. The timeliness of a dataset describes the difference in time between an electronically captured event in the real world and its digital representation in the dataset. Changes can result from new data being captured (e.g., a sale), existing data becoming outdated due to real-life events (e.g., a customer moving), or from data being deleted (e.g., a company going bankrupt).

Related terms: Up to date

Legal Background:

Timeliness is related to the factual accuracy (correctness) of personal data in Art. 5(1)(d) of the GDPR. There may be an obligation to update personal data if this is "necessary" from the perspective of the data subject in view of the purpose of the data processing. (Roßnagel/NK Data Protection Law, 1st edition 2019, Art. 5 para. 141.).

Traceability

Traceability describes the ability to trace the origin of data and all transformations that have been performed on data. This, for example, facilitates the restoration of data to a previous state, e.g. by using common version control systems or appropriate data sheets for documentation, so that either the current version is replaced or different versions of the data exist in parallel.

Related terms: Provenance, Lineage, recoverability

Transparency

The dimension of transparency includes disclosure requirements about the origin of training data, information about quality checks performed on datasets, about who labelled the datasets, what the learning goals are, whether and to what extent source code can be viewed, and more. Transparency enables individuals impacted by technical systems to make informed decisions and renders infringements to be identifiable and correctable. Transparency also facilitates societal debates and the building of trust.

Related terms: Interpretability, accessibility, documentation

Understandability

Data are in an understandable state if users can understand them immediately. Understandable data have a meaningful schema and use typical data formats. For example, an online store's data are understandable if the full name of articles is listed, so that customers can immediately recognise them. Understandability is impaired, for instance, if only an article number is listed instead of the full name.

Related terms: Explainability, Readability, Interpretability

Uniqueness

Uniqueness considers if each entity in the real world is represented as at most one data entity: there are no duplicates. For example, the same customer appears only once in a customer database – therefore the customer database contains no duplicates.

Related terms: Duplicate-free, redundancy-free

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